

How will the TRICK platform support policies to promote circularity on the textile, clothing and food value chains in Europe?

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Our main findings

This report presents a summary of the analysis of critical services, barriers and de-risking, for a transition from linear to circular in TRICK pilots carried out in the task T1.2 arousing policy makers interest. The task consisted on defining the connection between the needs of the final users and the technical development of the TRICK platform. It aimed to depict the needs, feelings, expectations, barriers and vision from the final user point of view.

This document emphasises the need of innovation, digitalization, collaboration and policies involvement to overcome the main barriers that the TRICK platform implementation will face as key factors to turn into a more transparent and sustainable industry. This brief summarizes the implication of policy makers on the following recommendations:

- Involving policy makers during the testing phases in order to ensure a direct impact on overcoming the identified barriers with the help of TRICK platform.
- Promoting the adoption of the TRICK platform among the textile and clothing (TC) and Food value chain to foster communication, collaboration and reliable and secure information transfer enhancing circularity in Europe.
- Encouraging the use of the TRICK platform to support policy making for decision making.
- Considering the TRICK platform as an assessment and standardization tool for certifications' recommendation.

This work contributes to policy issues and certifications from different perspectives:

- The requirements of policy makers' users were isolated and evaluated in the global framework and separately.
- On the side of certifications, the data gathering complied a set of mandatory certifications required to the different actors of the TC and food Value chain that will participate into the pilots.

1 Introduction

The TRICK project aims to develop a complete, reliable, SME-affordable and standardized platform to support the adoption, tracing and demonstration of sustainable and circular approached on the TC and food industry, secured by Blockchain enabling the enterprises to collect product-secured data.

The technical approach for **the development of a blockchain based platform requires a detailed set of requirements** to understand the user needs and expectations. T1.2 consisted on describing the use case scenarios needed for the implementation of a traceability system that improves transparency and promotes circularity on the TC and food industry in Europe, identifying opportunities and pain points at how to overcome them. The definition of the **design space is crucial to link the user needs with its technical development for the TRICK platform**. The outputs of this work reflect the complexity of the TC and food value chain and highlights the differences in usage that might be taken into account when designing the platform.

The approach has considered policy issues as an important and independent scenario, contemplated on a specific use cases. Also, a recap from the certifications more adopted and demanded by the final users is detailed.

2 Use Cases definition

Working on the definition of a design framework has to involve all the different points of view of the partners involved in the project and of the textile value chain stakeholders. For this purpose, a set of materials and collaborative tools were designed, which allowed to collect the data in an efficient and focused way. The analysis of the data aimed to detect similarities, patterns and stereotypes. Data was compiled on a set of scenarios, user needs, platform requirements and use cases. The project also identifies the service vision and the main barriers to overcome during the implementation, together with a high-level proposals of de-risking.

2.1 Scenarios

From the gathered information, **six scenarios** were identified corresponding to the different **TRICK stakeholders**. They have been classified in: **manufacturers, consumers, service providers, researchers, retailers, policy-makers** plus the **food** scenario.

Policy making and decision taking needs a **global vision of the whole value chain**. The **trustfulness and reliability** of the data are **key to ensure the wellness in terms of sustainability and ethics** of the TC and food sector towards a circular business model. Specifically, Policy markers' interest on TRICK has to tackle:

- To improve of transparency on the TC and food business and trade operations and of the data reliability and trustfulness.
- To ensure the fair adoption of policies towards circularity through measurable and actionable outcomes.

- To contribute to policies related to the transition from linear to circular.

The global vision of the TC and food sectors comes from the gathering and analysis of information from **several and diversified sources**. There is still a **relevant gap between the adoption of policies and the evaluation of the impacts generated**. TRICK platform will provide **key performance indicators** (KPIs) to check the trends related to business, environmental impact and social and health implications on the sector. Always ensuring the check of the veracity of the sources of data.

2.2 User Needs and Use Cases

From the scenario description, a set of user' needs and platform requirements were retrieved, Annex A lists the requirements regarding the Policy Makers' in detail. Four use cases were drawn on the basis of the needs of the users. Each use case corresponds to the **different purpose of use** when accessing the platform. All of them contemplate the **consultancy of information** stored by the platform, the **data insertion**, the **product development** of new services, based on TRICK information and existing services, and the **trading and business cases** that correspond to the regulation of the users' interactions. The latter, specifically addresses policy makers' interests, described on the basis of the requirements of the policy makers' scenario. The use cases are summarized in Annex B.

2.3 Vision

A **common service vision** is the key to keep all the project partners aligned and to have a clear target. It helps developers to understand the type of product that the user is expecting in a more tangible way. TRICK's statement is available in Annex C. Specifically, TRICK **allows the validation of regulation compliance and of the related impact indicators**. It tackles the issues involving waste management, production costs, environmental impact and data integrity shared across digital systems to give visibility to the whole value chain and unveils its impacts on decision taking among the chains. It **collects results and recommendations** from researchers and forward them in a comprehensive way to other interested stakeholders.

3 Policy implications and recommendations

The implementation of the TRICK platform has to overcome a set of barriers that have been organized in eight categories going from **technological, economical, legal, sector diversification, geographical, cultural, knowledge to design**, represented in Figure 1.

The main categories are represented on coloured boxes. The grey boxes correspond to the sub-categories of barriers, which can be approached considering different categories of barriers. Finally, the specific barriers are represented on boxes contoured with the colour of the category of barrier where they belong and placed on the corresponding sub-category.

Figure 1: Barriers implying policies organized on their corresponding categories and sub-categories

To overcome the identified barriers requires actions at policy level, which are detailed on the de-risking proposal. Specifically, policy making has a direct impact on the **overcoming of the legal and economic barriers**. In the following table, the policies to overcome the identified barriers are detailed with its corresponding de-risking proposal.

Regulation making

- To support policy makers with information regarding regulation compliance accounting the geographical differences, towards the **implementation and standard definition of a complete taxonomy** of the textile recycling that supports circularity and promotes regulations to be more appealing on the sector and converge to a new circular model.
- To give visibility of the whole value chain **unveiling the impacts on decision making and detecting bottlenecks** that help on identifying where is worth to apply incentives. This will be supported by analysis of the expected impacts and outcomes.

Market trends

- **To support new market trends relating circular economy** with relevant indicators to maximize the investment impact and revenues and benchmarking tools to aware of your competitiveness on the market.

Circular economy

- **To foster the performance** of the current **circular business models** and the creation of new ones by **providing the necessary data and transfer of information about the latest innovation and research** (Green chemistry, alternative recycling routes, waste

management, circular design...).

- **To demonstrate the improvement** and evolution of circular projects to **support the use of renewable sources and regeneration of the natural systems**. TRICK will give visibility of the benefits of changing towards a circular model.

Standardization of regulations and certification

- **To assess and recommend** the most convenient standards, easing the consultancy and certification, inherent to the PCO services and the block-chain based traceability. Standardized certifications as PEF can prevent from green-washing.

Communication and collaboration

- **To gather the different actors of the value chain** by sharing the appropriate information, by fostering collaboration, communication and cooperation towards circular economy. By means of promoting the connection with local business and the access to the information related to the existing circular solutions on the market empowering the final users.

Information transfer

- To encourage the **adoption of the platform** to become massively used by the industry stakeholders.

Transparency, traceability among the supply chain

- To support the collection of complete and reliable data among the supply chain **increasing the visibility of those companies which are more transparent**.

This activity takes into consideration **policy makers as key actors for the implementation and adoption of the platform** involving them in the **promotion of circular economy models to achieve the SDG and more sustainable and ethical policies in Europe**. Specifically, the following suggestions can be outlined:

- Involve policy makers during the testing phases in order to ensure a direct impact on overcoming the identified barriers with the help of the TRICK platform.
- Promote the adoption of the TRICK platform among the TC and Food value chain to foster communication, collaboration and reliable and secure information transfer enhancing circularity in Europe.
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4 Annexes

A. User need and requirements regarding policies

User need	Requirement
Digitized, reliable and trustful data	The system has to inform at a glance about the level of data reliability , the available certifications and their compliance with the standards.
Access to the appropriated data sets in compliance with confidentiality issues	Secured access, restricted to specific users , and effortless integration of data sets.
Visualization of aggregated updated data	Data aggregation and visualization in customizable dashboards, including trend charts, custom reports
Detection of bottlenecks and pain points	Data analysis to unveil bottlenecks , difficult actions, pain points and detect anomalies
Availability of data and disclosure to the users	Provide the origin of data and confidentiality rules applying, as well as the level of confidence of the data.

B. Trading and business use case

Description
TRICK will securely and trustfully handle and store data required for the PCO and related duty calculation. It will also facilitate the trade and business interaction with other actors of the value chain by the implementation of a dedicated marketplace.
User experience
TRICK will support the trading operations by bringing together the required documents and information and ensuring that they are provided to the right recipients only (like official custom agencies), protecting data privacy and preserving the associated certifications. It will ease the research of partners providing the description of their capabilities, products and services. Additionally, in the case of PCO, TRICK will allow the gathering of the necessary information to fulfil the legal requirements.
Fragmentation and complexity of the business network
TRICK will help to establish business relationships and to find the right service provider either at local or global level. Thus, it will reduce the the inconveniences associated to the fragmentation and complexity of the sector.
Privacy of data and data security
The access will be given depending on the specific category of the user and the related level of access privilege, permission and role on the platform.

Cost and affordability
The trading and business processed will be sped up aiming to support usual operations, thus reducing time, cost and improving competitiveness.
Technological barriers
Management of privacy and security while maintaining a complete communication between the involved stakeholders.

C. TRICK Vision Statement and description

TRICK service vision statement

TRICK platform is a digital platform that impulses **the transition from linear to circular model, by blockchain based innovative solutions** for the **traceability and transparency** within the TC and Food supply chains. It will provide **secure, transparent, reliable, relevant, high quality automated data** regarding products and manufacturing processes, in an **easy and reliable way**.

TRICK service vision description

TRICK platform assists the implementation of circular economy practices, **supporting certification and standard compliance** in all stages of the production pipeline. It offers a variety of digital services for calculating and communicating data.

Sets of complete and **trustful data and indicators** help **analyse, simulate critical points, provide suggestions and communicate** through the whole supply chain. Information and indicators are ready to use, allowing policy makers and regulators to **improve and track the impacts of the policies adopted**.

Blockchain-based platform ensures **traceability, security, and reliability data flows** throughout the production chains. The platform also uses **A.I. to allow data exploitation** for specific services.

The platform can be used across the TC and food supply chain in an **interoperable** way, allowing the replication of similar scenarios and ensuring the **scalability of the solution**. It can be **easily linked** with the existing users' **IT systems**. The service marketplace is accessible through web browsers and interoperable with enterprises' **ERPs**.

Users can easily access and register, accordingly to the role, which determines the access to the product information within the value chains.